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Rainfall Prediction

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Rainfall Prediction FAIR Experiment project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [Data Management and FAIR principles] section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Kaya Ali Kus will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	rainfall-prediction.ipynb	Serialised data file	ipynb	2MB	no
P2	1-model-logistic-regression-metadata.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No
P3	1-Logistic_Regression.pkl	Model	pkl	~1KB	no
P4	2-model-decision-tree-metadata.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No
P5	2-Decision_Tree.pkl	Model	pkl	~1-2MB	No
P6	3-model-mlp-metadata.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P7	3-Neural_Network.pkl	Model	pkl	~50KB	No
P8	4-model-random-forest-metadata.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No
P9	4-Random_Forest.pkl	Model	pkl	~130MB	No
P10	5-model-lightgbm-metadata.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No
P11	5-LightGBM.pkl	Model	pkl	~1MB	No
P12	6-model-catboost-metadata.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No
P13	6-CatBoost.pkl	Model	pkl	~50MB	No
P14	7-model-xgboost-metadata.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No
P15	7-XGBoost.pkl	Model	pkl	~15MB	No
P16	codemeta.json	Serialised data file	json	~1KB	No

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Rainfall Prediction Australia Weather Data - Train	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/p253-bv05	Copyright Commonwealth of Australia 2010, Bureau of Meteorology.	no
R2	Rainfall Prediction Australia Weather Data - Test	https://handle.test.datacite.org/10.82556/jt8x-8r64	Copyright Commonwealth of Australia 2010, Bureau of Meteorology.	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Research Data Reuse

Model Training: Multiple models were tested including Linear Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost, etc.

Methods for Data Reuse:

Pre-existing Datasets: Publicly available weather datasets from Kaggle were reused (e.g., "Weather Dataset – Rattle Package"). No additional external datasets were integrated.

Software Used:

Python:

pandas and NumPy for data manipulation.

matplotlib, seaborn for visualization.

scikit-learn for machine learning model training and evaluation.

Jupyter Notebook: For conducting and documenting the analysis.

DBRepo: For storing and managing datasets.

Outputs:

Trained models, fair4ml metadata for models, evaluation metrics, Jupyter Notebook (.ipynb) and CodeMeta metadata for the source code to reproduce the results.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Students and general public

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The dataset, sourced from the Rain in Australia collection, is organized in a structured tabular format (CSV file). Each row represents daily weather observations from various Australian locations, encompassing attributes such as date, location, temperature, humidity, wind speed, and rainfall. To manage versioning, each dataset iteration will be assigned a unique Persistent Identifier (PID) upon upload to DB Repo. This ensures that all updates or modifications are tracked systematically, allowing users to access specific versions and maintain reproducibility in analyses.

To ensure the dataset is easily identifiable, discoverable, and reusable, a comprehensive set of metadata will be provided. The Name of the dataset will be a clear and descriptive title. The Size of the dataset will also be indicated to inform users about the storage requirements. The License information will specify the terms under which the data can be used and shared, promoting open access and reuse. A detailed Description will summarize the dataset's contents, purpose, and its origin from sources such as Kaggle's Australian weather datasets. The Language used throughout the dataset, primarily English, will be clearly mentioned to support understanding and use. Finally, the Engines used for hosting and managing the dataset, such as "MariaDB: 11.1.3," will be documented, providing technical context for potential users. Keywords like "rainfall prediction," "weather data," "meteorology," and "machine learning" will be assigned to enhance the dataset's discoverability in search engines and repositories. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
1	Auth for API access	-	Already Public	DBRepo	eb0eaaaa-c5cf-4946-ac2b-79180adc7074	-
2	Auth for API access	-	Already Public	DBRepo	bb7df58b-99e8-4471-9cde-d45d578f7930	-

Repository description:

This project focuses on predicting rainfall using a combination of classic machine learning algorithms. We explore and compare the performance of 7 popular models to predict rainfall more accurately based on historical data.

Methods or software needed to access and use data: DBRepo, Python

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Data Description: Detailed explanations of each variable, including definitions, units of measurement, and any data transformations applied. Code Documentation: Annotated scripts and Jupyter notebook detailing the analytical workflow, including model selection, training, and evaluation. README: A comprehensive README file outlining the project's objectives, dataset structure, usage instructions, and contact information for further

inquiries. Results and Visualisations: Inclusion of performance metrics, charts, and graphs (e.g., confusion matrices, ROC curves) to illustrate model efficacy and support result interpretation. Reproducibility: All code and documentation will be hosted in a public GitHub repository, ensuring transparency and enabling other researchers to replicate the study.

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements, standardized data capture and representation with controlled vocabularies.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

All outputs Evaluation Images, Comparison Results, Source Code, Model metadata and Code metadata can be found at

- GitHub: <https://github.com/Kaya2134/Rainfall-Prediction> (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15295792>)
- TUWRD: <https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/p7rh4-0g783> (DOI: <https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/doi/10.70124/5kgbn-90w06>)

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with Kaya Ali Kus being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Kaya Ali Kus (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will not be stored on TU Wien servers.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

Information regarding rights and control of access to data has yet to be identified.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?